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Study Success in Course of TVET- Results of a Mixed-Methods study

Pletscher, Joana

Joana.pletscher@uni-kassel.de, University of Kassel Institute for Vocational Education and Training

Abstract

The shortage of vocational school teachers in the industrial-technical sector is glaring in Germany. This is a long-term problem. One way to address this problem is to analyze the success of TVET studies with the aim of deriving measures and mechanisms to increase success. This problem is addressed with a mixed-method design in order to quantitatively and qualitatively analyze factors influencing academic success. Particular attention is paid to the motives for choosing a course of study and subject, and to study behavior. It turns out that these are interrelated. The majority of First Generations students study with the clear professional goal of becoming vocational school teachers and show a strong goal orientation in their choice of studies as well as in their study behavior.

Keywords

study success, TVET studies, study behavior, study choice decision, mixed-methods design

1 Context

Calculating the numbers of teachers needed in Germany in the coming years shows an undersupply to be expected especially in industrial-technical subjects (Klemm 2018). Which measures could contribute to reduce the expected undersupply? Firstly, the reported low attractiveness of the study program and the profession have to be improved. Secondly, the high numbers of dropouts of students need to be addressed. While dropouts have been in the focus of research for several years, the success rates in study programs for Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) need to be examined in more detail. For example, Heinze (2018) shows that academic success is a process that is characterized not only by hard but also by multiple soft factors. That is, a bundle of factors during the process influence student success. Hard factors are, for instance, the study grades or the duration of study, as shown in the table below (Bornkessel 2018). According to Heinze (2018), soft factors include study satisfaction, the tendency to drop out and the increase in competence. Furthermore, the own participation in university or social peer groups play a role.

Table 1

Process model of study success (own representation according to Heinze 2018)

		Process Level:	Results Level:	
		Course of Studies	Study Degree	
Success Criteria	Hard Facts	Grades of individual exams	Degree	
		Number of exams (not) passed	Study Grade	
		Number of achieved credit points	Duration of Study	
	Soft Facts	Tendency of Dropout	Increase in competence	
		Tendency of Change the Course	Personality Development	
			Social / university commitment	
		Study Satisfaction		

Similar to the case of dropping out, numerous factors have an impact on academic success. These include, for example, age, own academic background, and the academic background of the parents. Thus Döppers (2022) assumes that students who have acquired their university entrance qualification at a vocational school have a lower cultural capital in the field of the university. They have to make a high adaptation performance in order to acquire appropriate cultural capital and to integrate themselves academically. Financing also has an influence on academic success. Financial uncertainties have a negative effect, as does a high workload. But Isleib and Woisch (2018) show that employment can have a positive impact if it is closely related to the subject of study. Study success is moreover influenced by the perception of the study conditions and the student's own ability to study. With reference to the clientele, study ability is seen as a multidimensional process, which is characterized by content-related, personal, social and organizational perspectives (Brutzer et al. 2022).

Ziegler (2014) already describes the students of the vocational school teaching profession as a heterogeneous group, which is characterized by upheavals in their educational biography. However, Döppers (2022) describes that the students themselves see the various decisions as a continuum or logical consequence of their previous education. It is generally agreed that students begin their studies with very different prerequisites. Wyrwall and Zinn (2018) identified a high proportion of students have completed vocational training beforehand and often come from a non-academic background and can thus be classified as First Generation Students (Grunau & Petzold-Rudolph 2021). In addition, the average age at the start of the program is three years higher than for traditional students (Döppers 2022). As a result, the students are often in different life situations. In this context it was issued that the students are strongly connected to their local area and thus often accept a longer commute (Wyrwall & Zinn 2018). These are factors that inhibit academic and social integration and thus have a negative impact on academic success. However, Döppers (2022) shows that the non-traditional students in particular benefit from their socialization in the vocational school in the TVET study program. The students' cultural capital from vocational school led to significantly better results, especially in the practical phases. Parts of their professional knowledge are transferable to university. Nevertheless, Wyrwall and Zinn (2018) among others show that students often have performance problems in mathematics. Sonntag (2018) attribute this to the time span between the acquisition of the university entrance qualification and the start of studies, as well as the lower study ability of students without a general university entrance qualification. In addition, the students not only have less cultural knowledge of the field of higher education (Döpper 2022), but also start their studies uninformed compared to students of the general teaching

profession or refer to information from third parties instead of using official information channels (Wyrwal & Zinn 2018). As a result, this group of students have very different prerequisites and correspondingly different needs for their studies. Fundamental for this group is the need for support and guidance. This results from a lower cultural capital and the socialization in educational institutions, which are very closely managed in contrast to university.

2 Approach

The path to academic success can be seen as a process jointly influenced by student- and university-related factors. This case study – trying to identify factors reducing dropouts and increasing academic success in the study program TVET Metal & Electrical Engineering at the University of Kassel – is focusing on two research questions:

1. Which factors influence the success of the course of studies in TVET program?
2. Which measures can increase the success of the course of studies on the part of the university?

To capture the specifics of the hard and soft factors of academic success as well as their interplay, a mixed-methods design was elaborated consisting of a document analysis (N=150) (Hoffmann 2018), problem-centered interviews (PCI) (n=18) (Witzel & Reiter 2022) and socio-demographic questionnaires (n=18). The focus is on the holistic recording of study success. The analysis is based on the content analysis according to Mayring (2015). Quantitative content analysis was used for the document analysis and summary content analysis was used for the interviews and questionnaires.

3 Results

Of the 150 individuals in the document analysis, 20 individuals were determined to be successful (Pletscher 2022). Of those, 18 agreed to be interviewed. Of these 18 people, only five have a high school diploma and the others have a subject-related university entrance qualification. All but three completed vocational training before beginning their studies. Only two reported that one parent had an academic degree. This shows that TEVT is studied primarily by people without academic background. However, the paths into the program are very heterogeneous. Some of the students started their TVET studies directly after obtaining their university entrance qualification. Others have tried out other courses of study or worked in business before starting their TVET program.

When asked why they (n=18) chose the TVET program, all students said that they were at a crossroads and had to make an educational decision. On the basis of their own teaching experiences, which they had made e.g. in training or professional practice, and in comparison, with other educational and professional options (e.g. further training as a technician), the decision to study TVET for them was a logical consequence of their previous education. Thus, the vocational training was not 'in vain'. In addition, almost all expressed that extrinsic factors (tenure, salary, regular work hours) also played a role in their decision to pursue TVET, often in comparison with the working conditions of their professions. Although they have chosen a new educational path, only three out of eighteen have attended an information session. Many said that they had talked to their teachers instead or with persons in their peer.

For example, all students (n=18) express that they set a short study time as a goal, but the numbers show that only three students met the standard study time. The results of the PCI indicated that the students proceed according to plan to the greatest possible extent. On the other hand, students also expressed that they have little knowledge about university cultures and this has presented them with problems. Likewise, all persons described problem in social integration and difficulties in arriving at the university.

Based on their experiences in vocational school, the majority of students attribute low importance to academic education. The reason is that, based on their own experience as students at vocational training, they do not see any added value in dealing with subject content at university level because they see that the level is not corresponding with the level they used to deal with in vocational school. Some even express that they only want to earn the certificate of completion or teaching credential or become an academic.

If you look at the statistics on the occupancy of the minors, you can already see that they influence the academic success differently (Pletscher 2022). In the PCI, it becomes clear that the motives for choice of minors have a considerable role. For example, some individuals cited ease of passing the courses as a reason for choosing them. While others cited professional or personal interest as a motive for choice. But no person found out about the minors in advance. Thus, the information on which the minor decision is based is often subjective and has never been tested for its truthfulness, and no one has been informed about the study conditions of his or her minor.

4 Conclusion

The student body is very heterogeneous and starting conditions vary greatly. This also coincides with findings by Wyrwal & Zinn (2018) and Ziegler (2014). It can be stated that the cultural capital and social and academic integration at university are important factors for reaching academic success. Factors such as educational attainment, study ability, prior information and the aforementioned problems with arriving at the university play a role here. In addition, there are the chosen major and minor subjects and the corresponding motives for taking them, which in turn are influenced by previous education. It is striking that the decision to study represents a concrete career choice for all of them.

Many problems, such as social and academic integration, as well as professional deficits, could be identified and remedied early if students received closer supervision. This is also in line with the findings of Wyrwal and Zinn (2018), who show that TVET students would like closer supervision. In addition, it would make sense to tailor the course more closely to the students and their needs. Döppers (2022) demonstrates that especially in projects with reference to professional and school practice, the prior knowledge of non-traditional students is connectable. If the teaching were to respond more strongly to these preconditions, professional deficits and a high number of failed exams could be avoided and the experience of competence could be strengthened.

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Biographical note

Joana Pletscher is an academic member and PhD student at the Department of Vocational Education and Training at the University of Kassel, Germany. Her research interests focus on study success, conditions of study and dropout in course of technical Vocational Education and Training.